

Good luck system safety

Asemova Rano Japbarbergenovna

Uzsanoatkurilishbank ATB

Call BXM .

Service manager chief specialist

It is known that in the republic in practice was Central of the bank interbank payment system of bank customers mainly " large " payments gross (each one payments according to separate) calculations based on again performance as well as Clearing system through " retail " payments system of members each one financial operations according to known one period during assembled requirements and obligations pure position determined without done increase opportunity creates It's past period Central of the bank interbank electron payment system improvement , system members and users for advanced technologies based on service show is also specific affairs done increased . Including the Republic Central bank from 2018 starting from new edited " Single representation accounts calculation center " software complex to practice current done programmatically in the complex payment documents in real time " sessions" mode based on file processing mode to give mechanism to work dropped . Central of the bank interbank thank you system through electron payment documents transition process the following in the scheme statement made by :

The banking system of our country is electronic payments system improvement about take going affairs result efficient it has been . Analyzes that's it shows that

Central of the bank interbank payment system through 2017 the first 37.6 million in half . or 318.7 trillion . soum interbank payment documents done increased if , current of the year the first in half while this the indicator is 36.3 million . know or 385.3 trillion . soum organize is doing Being compared period Central of the bank interbank thank you system through past payment documents number to 3.5 percent reduced payment documents amount and 20.8 percent that it has increased note reach it is permissible .

Money of treatment high efficient system organize reach and modern thank you mechanisms apply country economy development necessary is a condition . Entrepreneurship subjects between don't turn around increased going trust wakes up payment obligations own on time and right in execution . Money of flow violation material work to issue negative effect it does while service does whole of the country financial resources of formation basis . Modern economic in the system diary economic circulation participants goods , services and financial assets exchange according to many operations done increase , this while own in turn money calculations through done is increased . National economy mechanism of activity efficiency payment in systems payments and of calculations continuous , fast and safe done increase depend Scientific and technical progress in the country payment and calculation relationships change process is inciting . Thank you forms and methods of payment tools is changing , showing payment of services speed , reliability and quality increase , payment operations according to transaction expenses reduce for the most new information technologies current is being done . With that together with this of the field fast development thank you to systems special has been of dangers to increase take will come .

Management of the Central Bank command with Payment systems operators and payment services delivered of the givers payment in systems information safety and cyber security provide and digital technologies by means of happen to be done offenses prevention get measures to see about statute confirmed .

President decision with digital consumers of products (services) . rights protection to do and digital technologies by means of happen to be done to offenses against to fight strengthen measures defined .

Confirmed statute the following defines :

- thank you information protection to do mechanisms ;
- thank you of information confidentiality and in them to the individual circle information protection to do
- information safety and cyber security of service duties ;

- information systems employees powers ;
- information networks from attacks protection to do order and information systems and resources monitoring , information safety and cyber security requirements violation with dependent events determination ;
 - information safety and of cyber security to the violation relationship notice measures ;
 - important thank you systems to the operators information safety and cyber security provide according to to be placed requirements ;
 - bank and thank you in systems suspicious fraud operations against measures to see of service duties and others

The interbank payment system is designed to make electronic payments between banks in the national currency (Soum) through representative accounts of banks opened at the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The rules of the interbank payment system are determined by the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The interbank payment system of the Central Bank is implemented in accordance with the following legal documents:

Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan" (December 21, 1995, No. 154-I)

Uzbekistan Republic of Banks and banking about". Law (25.04.1996, No. 216-I)

Uzbekistan Republic of " Elektron payments about". Law (16.12.2005, No. O'RQ-13)

Central of the bank interbank thank you system through electron payments done increase order about". Regulation (14.02.2006, No. 1545)

" Uzbekistan in the Republic cash without money calculations about". Regulation (03.06.2013 No. 2465)

Interbank thank you system Uzbekistan Republic Central of the bank personal property is considered Central of the bank General Information Center and Central of the bank calculations center interbank thank you system participants is considered Interbank thank you system users Central of the bank Calculations in the center representation to the account have has been banks and financial institutions is considered